

**Engaging Crowds:
citizen research
and heritage data at scale.**

**A response to the
Advisory Board Report
February 2022**

by

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Recommended citation: Leachman, S. (February 2022) *Engaging Crowds: citizen research and heritage data at scale. A response to the Advisory Board Report February 2022.*
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RBziMPY8s0iPg58Bao60qKnP6RBGIW5OtwhiJ5TOqqw>

Project summary

Firstly I would like to offer my congratulations to all the participants and organisations taking part in this Project. Having read the February report I have been very impressed by the progress and the achievements made by everyone involved. To get the various Zooniverse projects off the ground, to engage so many volunteers with the content, and to obtain usable data from this engagement, is no mean feat. The progress made in improving and developing the Zooniverse platform has also been impressive and I feel that these achievements should be acknowledged at the outset, given how hard everyone involved must have worked to get to this point.

After reading the report, I would also like to highlight just a few of the elements outlined there that I was particularly impressed by.

Royal Museums Greenwich

Firstly Royal Museums Greenwich. I thought the launch of Part Two of their zooniverse project to coincide with the Who Do You Think You Are? Magazine's Transcription Tuesday event was inspired. What a wonderful way to reach out to an audience that is keen to transcribe and to encourage and enable them to engage with that institution's content.

I also thought the iterative approach regarding dropdown options in the project was wise and was effective in ensuring the best outcome for both the institution and its volunteers. This counterintuitive result, that is that dropdown menus decreased volunteer agency, is an area that is ripe for further study and research. Particularly as there is often a tension between the desire to ensure volunteer agency and the need for accurate data generation, often the motivation for adding dropdown menus when designing crowdsourcing projects.

The National Archives

I was impressed that the National Archives project managed to attract over 500 volunteers and in particular that the project was completed in only a few weeks. This was especially impressive given the need for lengthy instructions and the relatively long and complex workflows.

In my view, the fact that a handful of volunteers contributed to the Talk forums should be taken as a sign of a successful crowdsourcing project. Those "handful" are highly motivated

and deeply engaged volunteers. By contributing to the Talk forums they show they are passionate about the content offered by the National Archives. As the report points out, these volunteers have extended their engagement with the project content, undertaken their own research and provided technical support to their fellow volunteers. To me, this is a clear sign of project success. It aligns well with my experience with several other successful crowdsourcing projects. That is, that the core group of highly engaged volunteers tends to be small but that the impact of their engagement with the project, both on the institution and on themselves, is significant. Congratulations on getting as many as a “handful”, as other projects only manage one or two such powerfully engaged and motivated volunteers.

Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh

As for the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh, I was impressed by how well the institution responded to having to alter how the transcription tasks were approached by volunteers. That the volunteers completed the workflow on the Latitude/Longitude in only 7 days is a wonderful achievement. In my view, that the Talk forums were so active on the Geography part of the workflow, is also a sign of success. Although this support of volunteers does take time and resources, this type of contact also encourages volunteers to engage more deeply with the content on the project and also ensures the data generated from this more complex workflow is of better quality.

Zooniverse

I would also like to congratulate the Zooniverse team for their work on creating and developing the new index tool. Both the back and front end developments and improvements outlined in the report and in the linked blog post are impressive. I can immediately see the potential for use of this tool in transcription projects, for example where a volunteer is experienced and used to transcribing a particular person's handwriting. To me it makes absolute sense to empower a volunteer who has expert knowledge in a particular area to guide their contributions via the indexing tool. This will have the effect of improving the accuracy and efficiency of their crowdsourcing efforts.

Feedback on Licensing conditions for each project.

I read with interest those sections of the report that gave information on the licensing conditions for each project. I would like to take this opportunity to give feedback to each institution on their reuse licensing.

Royal Museums Greenwich

I note that on page 15 to 16 of the Advisory Report February 2022, the Royal Museums Greenwich states that the data from its project is covered by Crown Copyright and that the data would be made available under the terms of the Open Government licence which is compatible with the Creative Commons Attribution Licence 4.0.

I want to point out that the next sentence following this statement in the report is in error. That is that “Users can re-use the data for non commercial research, education and private study”. This is incorrect. Under the Open Government licence the only restriction on reuse of the Royal Museums Greenwich data will be the requirement that the reuser acknowledge the source of the data.

Reusers can copy, redistribute, and adapt the data for any purpose, even commercially, so long as they give appropriate credit and, where appropriate, provide a link to the Open Government licence.

You are free to:

- copy, publish, distribute and transmit the Information;
- adapt the Information;
- exploit the Information commercially and non-commercially for example, by combining it with other Information, or by including it in your own product or application.

You must (where you do any of the above):

- acknowledge the source of the Information in your product or application by including or linking to any attribution statement specified by the Information Provider(s) and, where possible, provide a link to this licence;

If the Information Provider does not provide a specific attribution statement, you must use the following:

Contains public sector information licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0.

I would recommend that this be corrected in the report.

I am extremely pleased to see that Royal Museums Greenwich is intending to reuse the project data by integrating it into its own catalogue. I think this helps achieve one of the main goals volunteers would have had in contributing to the Dreadnought Seamen’s Hospital project - that is, assist the Royal Museums Greenwich in enriching the collection content and metadata about the same.

However, I feel I should point out that this integration, although useful to the Royal Museums Greenwich, is itself unlikely to assist with the more general goal of enabling reuse of Project data by the wider public. This is because the terms and conditions of reuse of the Royal Museums Greenwich website are themselves extremely restrictive. See <https://www.rmg.co.uk/terms-conditions> for more detail on those restrictions.

To avoid any issues or conflicts with the terms and conditions on the Royal Museums Greenwich website, I would recommend adding a link in the Royal Museums Greenwich catalogue to the Dreadnought Seamen's Hospital Open Government licenced dataset that is to be placed on the Engaging Crowds project website.

If, in addition to incorporating it into their catalogue, Royal Museums Greenwich decides to add the dataset in its entirety to their website, I would recommend that a clear reuse statement also be added indicating that this dataset is licensed for reuse under the Open Government Licence.

These efforts would enable the reuse of the Open Government licensed dataset without reusers being put off or confused by the more restrictive terms and conditions of the Royal Museums Greenwich website.

As regards the original images upon which the Dreadnought Seamen's Hospital project was based, obviously I would prefer if the Royal Museums Greenwich had more generous terms for reuse for those original images. However I recognise that these reuse terms may be dictated by the contract with Ancestry and also that each institution is on its own journey as regards the sharing and reuse of its collections.

I hold hope that at some point in the future the Royal Museums Greenwich will take steps to ensure the wider public have a greater ability to engage with that institution's collections through reusing the same, by providing more generous terms of reuse in its catalogue and on its website.

The National Archives

I am impressed that The National Archives was transparent with its volunteers and clearly explained that, when contributing, the volunteers were assigning the rights to any material they created to the Crown. I am also very pleased to see that the data contributed by the volunteers is licensed for reuse under an Open Government Licence.

When the data is published on the Engaging Crowds project website I recommend that this reuse licence is clearly stated in order to give guidance to visitors on what can be done with the data.

I am pleased to see that the volunteer transcriptions will be reused to enhance The National Archives catalogue and that The National Archives also intends to use these transcriptions for other research purposes. I believe this reuse helps achieve one of the main goals volunteers would have had in contributing to the Scarlets and Blues project - that is, assist The National Archive in enriching their collection content and metadata.

As regards the original images upon which the project was based, again, obviously I would prefer if The National Archives had more generous terms for reuse for those original images rather than restricting reuse to research, private study or education only. However again I recognise that each institution is on its own journey as regards the sharing and reuse of its collections.

Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh

I am extremely excited and pleased to see that the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh images are shared under a CC BY licence and that the associated data is licensed under the CC0 licence. This is fabulous and I want to commend the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh for taking this step and facilitating the open reuse of their collections.

Unfortunately at present these reuse terms are not immediately obvious when searching the RBGE online catalogue <http://data.rbge.org.uk/herb>. I was unable to find them when looking through the catalogue and exploring the website. I would therefore recommend that a statement be added to the RBGE website explaining these reuse conditions. I would also recommend that the "Citing the RBGE collections" page be updated to reflect the appropriate citation needed to comply with the reuse of content under these licences.

<https://www.rbge.org.uk/science-and-conservation/herbarium/visiting-the-herbarium/citing-rbge-herbarium-specimens/>

I am very pleased to see that each specimen has a stable URL allowing for citations and facilitating reuse. I am also excited to see that the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh is using multiple third party platforms in order to expand the access to, as well as the reach of, the

RBGE collections. This will definitely ensure greater reuse of and engagement with their collections.

I recognise that the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh has only recently made the change to its reuse policy and that this change may take time to filter through to third party platforms. However I should point out that , when accessing the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh specimen collections via Europeana, I found that the images and data are currently licensed under a CC-BY NC SA 3.0 licence <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/> See for example

<https://www.europeana.eu/en/item/11616/OPENUPXSPECIMENSXRBGEXUKXE00678359>.

I also took the liberty to check the reuse licences for Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh images and data stored in GBIF. Unfortunately similar issues also arise on this platform. Both the [Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh Herbarium](#) dataset and the [Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh Living Plant Collections](#) datasets are licensed for reuse under a CC-BY NC SA 4.0 licence.

When looking at a particular record in the Royal Botanic Garden Herbarium dataset the reuse licensing becomes confusing as it does not appear consistent with the policy set out in the report. See for example <https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/1228023560> This specimen lists the “record licence” at the top left, that is the licence for the image, as being CC0 whereas the data reuse licence, listed in the body of the metadata, is CC-BY NC SA 4.0. The CC0 image licence is repeated at the bottom of the web page - although you have to scroll along in the text box in order to see it. I have screenshotted the images for convenience.

MULTIMEDIA			
Associated Specimen Reference	Format	Owner	Creator
https://iiif.rbge...00622950/manifest	application/ld+json	Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh	Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh
http://data.rbge.org.uk/herb/E00622950	image/jpeg	Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh	Specimen Digitisation Pipeline

MULTIMEDIA				
Identifier	Rights	Service Expectation	Accessuri	Type
E00622950	Copyright Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh.	IIIF	https://iiif.rbge...00622950/manifest	InteractiveResource
E00622950	Copyright Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh. Contact us for rights to commercial use.	JPEG	http://repo.rbge....1MC85Mzk2NTIuanBn	StillImage

MULTIMEDIA			
	Type	Description	Rights
rbge...00622950/manifest	InteractiveResource	IIIF Manifest for specimen E00622950	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
.rbge....1MC85Mzk2NTIuanBn	StillImage	Image of herbarium specimen E00622950 by Specimen Digitisation Pipeline	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/

I assume that work is underway to ensure these reuse licences are updated to the licences outlined in the report. If not, I recommend that this be undertaken, particularly as currently the image reuse licence in GBIF is even more generous than that expressed in the report.

I commend the Royal Botanic Garden Herbarium not just for their intention to reuse the data created by volunteers but also having a workaround should integrating this data be a challenge. I believe this reuse helps achieve one of the main goals volunteers would have had in contributing to the Exploring Gesneriaceae project - that is, to assist the Royal Botanic Garden Herbarium in enriching their collection content and metadata.

Data sharing platform

In general I am enthusiastic that the Project is planning to create a dedicated space on the Engaging Crowds project website for this data and will be including links to the associated images.

My advice would be to ensure that the reuse licensing of those data is clearly stated on each dataset placed on the website with links to the appropriate Open Government Licence or Creative Commons Licence.

I would encourage the institutions who control the datasets to consider creating or generating a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for each dataset. I would encourage the Project

participants to consider uploading the project datasets into a platform such as Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/>. This would ensure the datasets are exposed to a wider audience while at the same time generating DOIs for the datasets.

DOIs would assist with ease of citation and also ensure the reuse of these data can be more easily tracked by the contributing institutions. This ability to gather information on reuse would likely assist with generating longer term impact metrics for this Project.

I recommend that the institutions draft and add a “recommended citation” for each dataset. This would assist researchers and other reusers of those data to comply with the Open Government Licence or Creative Commons licence under which the data is published.

Once the data is published on the Project website I would encourage the Project participants to archive both the website and its datasets. In particular I would recommend that the Project website along with each of the dataset URLs be archived in the Internet Archive via that organisation's Wayback Machine. This would go some way to mitigating the risk of losing the data should the Project Website become obsolete or eventually deleted.

How can we make sure that the results of Engaging Crowds feed into the mission to ‘take the first steps towards creating a unified virtual ‘national collection’ by dissolving barriers between different collections – opening UK heritage to the world.’

In order to create a unified virtual “national collection” connections between collections between collections need to be cultivated. One way to achieve this is to ensure that content, catalogues and records from one institution are connected to other institutions' content, catalogues and records. This interlinking can be done either by the institutions themselves, by adding such content to their databases, or as a member of a group tasked with creating a platform that enables this linking, or via third party platforms such as Wikidata. Whomever does the work, in order to make these links, stable urls and identifiers will be needed to facilitate this effort.

I was pleased to see in the report that the Royal Botanic Garden Herbarium has already implemented stable URLs for their collection. I would encourage the other two institutions, if they haven't already, to consider undertaking this necessary work so that their collections might also be more easily connected to others.